

APPLICATION OF ISOTENSOID-BASED CROSS SECTIONS TO FILAMENT-WOUND TOROIDAL PRESSURE VESSELS

L. Zu, S. Koussios and A. Beukers

Design and Production of Composite Structures, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering
Delft University of Technology, Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands

E-mail: L.Zu@tudelft.nl

SUMMARY

In this paper we evaluate the effect the application of isotensoid-based cross sections has on the geometry and performance of toroids. The cross-sectional shapes of such toroids are specially derived for providing uniformly stressed fibers. The isotensoid toroids result in significantly lighter structures than circular toroids at equal volumes.

Keywords: Composite pressure vessels, Filament winding, Toroids, Isotensoid-based cross-sections, Circular cross-sections

INTRODUCTION

Composite toroidal pressure vessels show great potential in the commercial and aerospace industries because of their structural efficiency, new-fashioned configuration, and low aspect ratio. A toroid can be regarded as a bent, endless cylinder that saves on the need for material in the end caps. As a shape, it is thus at least as structurally efficient as a cylinder. So far, the winding process of convex bodies has been studied for many years and the production of axisymmetrically wound parts such as cylinders, spheres and domes has become relatively simple and mature [1~4]. However, little research has been devoted to the winding of toroidal structures, and mostly limited to the design of circular toroids. Zu et al. [5,6] presented an optimization method for non-geodesically overwound toroids and developed a CAD system for their design and production. Li et al. [7] outlined a full mathematical approach to the design of overwound toroidal vessels using a membrane shell theory, considering the load-bearing capability of the wound layer and its interaction with the metallic liner. Jiang et al. [8] developed a novel winder for producing toroidal pressure vessels, based on the optimal design of the corresponding winding patterns.

The design of filament-wound toroids must take full account of the stress field as well as the material properties. Constraints imposed by the manufacturing process need to be respected, and the geometry that may restrict the structural efficiency must be properly determined. One of the shortcomings of the application of circular cross sections to toroids is that the tensile strength of the filaments cannot be completely

utilized, because the structural efficiency of a toroid is entirely governed by the cross-sectional shape. Previous investigations merely considered the architecture of reinforcement layers, but overlooked the design of adapted cross-sectional shapes (i.e. meridian profiles) for toroids. It is thus desirable to obtain the most efficient cross-sectional shapes for these structures. A new possibility to improve the performance of toroidal vessels has been offered by Koussios et al. [9,10] in which a novel configuration combining isotensoids with toroids is developed.

In this paper we outline a design-oriented method for determining the cross-sectional shapes of isotensoid toroids under internal pressure and axial load. First, the minimum strain energy criterion is used to determine the optimality relation for the winding angles and shell stresses of a general laminate, in order to maximize the load bearing capacity of such structures. Then, with the aid of the netting theory and geodesic winding law, the determination for the cross-sectional shapes of isotensoidal toroids is carried out to obtain constant fiber stress throughout the whole structure, taking into account the laminate thickness build-up along the meridional direction. The influence of the theoretically required axial load on the isotensoid meridian shape to close it is also evaluated. Lastly, the calculations and comparisons of cross-sectional shapes and structural masses of circular and isotensoid toroids are carried out to indicate that isotensoid toroids form a preferable alternative for the design of toroidal structures.

OPTIMALITY CONDITION FOR MINIMIZING STRAIN ENERGY

We consider here a symmetric laminate under in-plane loads (N_φ , N_θ) as shown in Fig. 1. The linear-elastic strain energy density of the laminate due to the in-plane forces is given by:

$$U = \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_\varphi \varepsilon_\varphi + \sigma_\theta \varepsilon_\theta + \tau_{\varphi\theta} \gamma_{\varphi\theta}) \quad (1)$$

where σ_{ij} and ε_{ij} ($i,j=\varphi,\theta$) are the in-plane stress and strain components for the laminate relative to the shell coordinate axis (φ - θ coordinate system).

Fig.1. A symmetric laminate under in-plane loads (N_φ , N_θ)

Since there is rotational symmetry for the shape and the applied load (internal pressure, axial force, etc), the shear stress and strain components in Eq. (1) must vanish. The constitutive equation of a symmetric laminate in the shell coordinate system is given by the classical lamination theory as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_\varphi \\ N_\theta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_\varphi \\ \varepsilon_\theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where A_{ij} represent the extensional stiffness components of the laminate. The inverse form of Eq. (2) is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_\varphi \\ \varepsilon_\theta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} N_\varphi \\ N_\theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where a_{ij} ($i,j=1,2$) denote the components of the compliance matrix $[a]$, expressed in terms of the extensional stiffnesses A_{ij} ($i,j=1,2$):

$$a_{11} = \frac{A_{22}}{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}, \quad a_{22} = \frac{A_{11}}{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}, \quad a_{12} = a_{21} = -\frac{A_{12}}{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2} \quad (4)$$

Substituting Eqs. (3) and (4) into Eq. (1) gives:

$$U = \frac{N_\varphi^2}{2} \frac{A_{22} - 2\eta A_{12} + \eta^2 A_{11}}{A_{22}A_{11} - A_{12}^2} \quad (5)$$

where η is the ratio of the in-plane shell forces (membrane forces) in parallel and meridional directions, given by:

$$\eta = \frac{N_\theta}{N_\varphi} \quad (6)$$

The following invariant equation is provided for the given ply configuration:

$$A_{11} + 2A_{12} + A_{22} = C \quad (7)$$

where C is the constant value, which is determined by the commonly known material constants and the layer thicknesses.

Next we will obtain the optimal laminate configuration for minimizing the strain energy density in Eq. (5), subjected to the equality constraint Eq. (7). Introducing this constraint with the aid of the Lagrange multiplier β , we should minimize the following augmented function:

$$f(A_{11}, A_{22}, A_{12}) = \frac{N_\varphi^2}{2} \frac{A_{22} - 2\eta A_{12} + \eta^2 A_{11}}{A_{22}A_{11} - A_{12}^2} - \beta(A_{11} + 2A_{12} + A_{22} - C) \quad (8)$$

Here the components of the extensional stiffness A_{ij} ($i,j=1,2$) are considered as the design variables. The minimum conditions are active when:

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial A_{11}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial A_{22}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial A_{12}} = 0 \quad (9)$$

The simultaneous solution of Eq. (9) in conjunction with the constraint Eq. (7) results in the optimal relation for the ratio of shell stresses and the extensional stiffnesses:

$$\eta = \frac{A_{22} + A_{12}}{A_{11} + A_{12}} \quad (10)$$

Assuming the winding angle α is always constant through the thickness direction, the components of extensional stiffness matrix A_{ij} are given by:

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{Q}_{ij}^k \cdot t_k = \bar{Q}_{ij} \cdot t \quad (i,j=1,2) \quad (11)$$

where \bar{Q}_{ij} , t are the reduced stiffness components and the total thickness of the laminate, respectively.

By substitution of Eq. (10) into (2), one can find that the strain at each point is the same in all directions, which is given by:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{N_\varphi}{A_{11} + A_{12}} \quad (12)$$

DESIGN OF ISOTENSOID TOROIDS

In this section we provide the design approach for determining the cross-sectional shapes of isotensoid toroids. The geometry and applied loads of a general isotensoid meridian is given in Fig. 2. $S(\theta, z)$ represents the vector of a shell of revolution in polar coordinates, given by:

$$S(\theta, z) = \{r(z) \cos \theta, r(z) \sin \theta, z\} \quad (13)$$

where θ denotes the angular coordinate in parallel direction, while r and z stand for the radial and axial distance.

Fig.2. Loads and geometry of a shell meridian

Governing Equations of Isotensoids

Under an internal pressure p and an externally applied axial load A , the axial equilibrium of the shell is given by:

$$A + \pi r^2 p = 2\pi r N_m / \sqrt{1 + r'^2} \quad (14)$$

in which N_m is the shell force in meridional direction, and r' is the first derivative of r with respect to z .

The force N_m can be obtained from Eq. (15):

$$N_m = \left(\frac{A}{2\pi r} + \frac{pr}{2} \right) \sqrt{1 + r'^2} \quad (15)$$

Only the netting theory is employed in this study. The filaments are assumed to carry all the loads and the burst of a pressure vessel takes place due to fiber fracture, that is, the stiffness of the matrix is considered negligible in comparison to the fiber strength. Thus the following relation holds true:

$$\sigma = E_f \cdot \varepsilon \quad (16)$$

where E_f is the Young's elastic module of the fibers, σ is the stress of the filament.

Substituting Eq. (11) into (12) and plugging the result into Eq. (16) yields:

$$\sigma = \frac{N_m}{t \cos^2 \alpha} \quad (17)$$

After substituting Eq. (15) into (17), the fiber stress at any point can be expressed as:

$$\sigma = \frac{\left(\frac{A}{2\pi r} + \frac{pr}{2} \right) \sqrt{1 + r'^2}}{t \cos^2 \alpha} \quad (18)$$

Considering the geometrical condition at the equator ($r=R$, $r'=0$), the fiber stress at the equator is given by:

$$\sigma_0 = \frac{\left(\frac{A}{2\pi R} + \frac{pR}{2} \right)}{t_0 \cos^2 \alpha_0} \quad (19)$$

The aim of the isotensoid design is to determine the meridian profile providing equal fiber tension everywhere. To achieve this goal, the fiber stress at any point should be equal to that at the equator. Thus we have:

$$\frac{\left(\frac{A}{2\pi r} + \frac{pr}{2} \right) \sqrt{1 + r'^2}}{t \cos^2 \alpha} = \frac{\left(\frac{A}{2\pi R} + \frac{pR}{2} \right)}{t_0 \cos^2 \alpha_0} \quad (20)$$

In calculating the thickness, the following two assumptions are made: first the fiber volume fraction is maintained consistently; secondly the number of filaments in a cross section is always constant. With these assumptions, the thickness along the meridional direction is given by [11]:

$$\frac{t}{t_0} = \frac{R}{r} \cdot \frac{\cos \alpha_0}{\cos \alpha} \quad (21)$$

This study considers the geodesic condition in which Clairant's equation is satisfied:

$$r \sin \alpha = r_0 \quad (22)$$

where r_0 is the polar opening radius.

We introduce:

$$\rho = \frac{r}{R}, \quad \zeta = \frac{z}{R}, \quad a = \frac{A}{\pi p R^2} \quad (23)$$

Substitution of equations (21), (22) and (23) into (20) leads, after expressing the winding angle in terms of ρ and ρ_0 , to:

$$\rho' = \sqrt{\frac{(a+1)^2(\rho^2 - \rho_0^2)}{\rho^2(a + \rho^2)^2(1 - \rho_0^2)}} - 1 \quad (24)$$

The above governing equation provides the shapes of isotensoid meridian profiles for various $\{a, \rho_0\}$ values. The equation has two pairs of real, and one pair of imaginary roots. This expression is only valid for the interval $[\rho_{\min}, 1]$ (selected positive real solutions by setting the argument of the denominator equal to zero), where ρ_{\min} is generally bigger than ρ_0 . For a given opening radius ρ_0 , the resulting meridian profile will strongly depend on the a -value. The $\{a, \rho_0\}$ -parameter set is able to completely determine the cross-sectional shapes of the isotensoids.

Fig.3. Influence of the axial force on the resulting isotensoid meridian profile

Cross-sectional Shapes of Isotensoid Toroids

Depending on the magnitude of the axial forces as related to the internal pressure, several isotensoid meridian profiles are obtained (see Fig. 3). When the axial force is sufficiently large for forcing the resulting meridian profile to become closed, the shape of the isotensoid becomes a toroid. Note that the tensional forces of the rovings that proceed from the polar area towards the equator replace here the theoretically required external axial force A , which is applied on the polar cap. Such a toroid would have a spherical cross-section in the case of isotropic materials; however, due to the anisotropic character of the reinforced wall the resulting cross-sectional shape is quasi-elliptic. The resulting meridian profiles, i.e. cross-sections of isotensoid toroids for different polar openings, are shown in Fig. 4. The isotensoid toroid belongs to the class of doubly curved surfaces, and is an interesting alternative for spaces having limited height.

Fig.4. Resulting cross sectional shapes for iso-toroids with various ρ_0

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section the difference of structural masses between circular and isotensoid toroids is calculated to demonstrate the favorable performance of toroids with isotensoid-based cross sections.

Internal Volume and Structural Mass

The dimensionless internal volume and structural mass are defined as follows:

$$\bar{V} = V / 2R^3, \quad \bar{M} = M \cdot \frac{X_T}{2\gamma p \pi R^3} \quad (25)$$

The dimensionless volume of an isotenoid toroid is then given by:

$$\bar{V}_{iso} = \int_0^{\delta_m} \pi \rho^2 d\zeta \quad (26)$$

where ζ_m is the maximum height of the meridian profile, at which the first derivative of ρ tends to infinity. When setting the denominator of Eq. (24) equal to zero, the radial coordinate ρ_m of the maximum point can be calculated as follows:

$$a + \rho_m^2 = 0 \Rightarrow \rho_m = \sqrt{-a} \quad \text{where } a < 0 \quad (27)$$

With the aid of *Runge-Kutta* formulae, ζ_m can be further calculated by Eq. (24):

$$\zeta_m = \zeta(\rho) \Big|_{\rho=\sqrt{-a}} \quad (28)$$

The structural mass can be calculated by:

$$M_{iso} = \int_0^{\zeta_m} 4\pi r t \sqrt{1+r'^2} dz \quad (29)$$

Solving Eq. (22) for the winding angle α and substituting the result into Eq. (18), the thickness distribution of isotenoid toroids is obtained by:

$$t = \frac{\left(\frac{A}{2\pi r} + \frac{pr}{2}\right) \sqrt{1+r'^2}}{X_T(1-r_0^2/r^2)} \quad (30)$$

By substitution of Eq. (30) into (29), the mass (in dimensionless form) is given by:

$$\bar{M}_{iso} = \int_0^{\zeta_m} \frac{\rho^2(\rho^2+a)(\rho'^2+1)}{\rho^2-\rho_0^2} d\zeta \quad (31)$$

The dimensionless internal volume and mass of a circular toroid are given by the expressions [12]:

$$\bar{V}_c = \frac{\pi^2(1+\rho_0)(1-\rho_0)^2}{8} \quad (32)$$

$$\bar{M}_c = \frac{(1-\rho_0)^2 \sqrt{(3+\rho_0)(5+\rho_0)}}{8} \int_0^\pi \frac{1}{\sin \alpha} d\varphi \quad (33)$$

where ρ_0 is the relative bend radius of torus.

Evaluations and Comparisons

To equalize the internal volume of an isotenoid toroid with that of a circular one, the cross-sectional shape of an isotenoid toroid is obtained using *Newton-Raphson* method. When a relative bend radius ρ_0 is assigned, the minimum radial distance ρ_{\min} of an isotenoid toroid is calculated by setting Eq. (26) equal to Eq. (32). The relations for the relative bend radii of equal-volume isotenoid and circular toroids are shown in Fig.5. Fig. 6 displays the distribution of internal volumes of isotenoid and circular toroids respectively, corresponding to various relative bend radii. The results indicate that the internal volumes of circular and isotenoid toroids can be equal only if the relative bend

radius of the circular toroid is above 0.29. Fig. 7 depicts the cross-sectional shapes of isotensoid and circular toroids at equal volumes. It is shown that the aspect ratio of the isotensoid meridian profile is always less than that of the circular one and increases with the raise of relative bend radius. Additionally, the isotensoid-based cross-sectional shape becomes identical with the circular one at small internal volumes and large bend radii.

Fig.5. Relative bend radii for isotensoid and circular toroids at equal volumes

Fig.6. Internal volumes of isotensoid and circular toroids with ρ_0

(1) $\rho_0 = 0.3, \bar{V} = 0.786$

(2) $\rho_0 = 0.4, \bar{V} = 0.622$

(3) $\rho_0 = 0.5, \bar{V} = 0.463$

(4) $\rho_0 = 0.6, \bar{V} = 0.316$

(5) $\rho_0 = 0.7, \bar{V} = 0.189$

(6) $\rho_0 = 0.8, \bar{V} = 0.089$

Fig.7. Cross-sectional shapes of isotenoid and circular toroids at equal volumes

The total masses of circular and isotenoid toroids are calculated at equal volumes. Fig. 8 illustrates the comparison of dimensionless masses of isotenoid and circular toroids, as a function of internal volume. The results show that the isotenoid toroid is consistently lighter than the circular one at any equal volume. The mass values of isotenoid toroids show about 30% maximal reduction compared with circular toroids. It is therefore desirable to employ isotenoid-based cross sections for the design and production of toroidal pressure structures.

Fig.8. Dimensionless masses of isotenoid and circular toroids at equal volumes

CONCLUSIONS

The main goal of this paper is to provide a design method for determining the cross-sectional shapes of isotenoid toroids, and to evaluate the effect of the isotenoid design on the geometry and performance of toroids. The results indicate that the isotenoid meridian curve can only become closed if the axial load reaches a sufficient value. The cross-sectional shapes of isotenoid toroids have been determined for various internal volumes, and the structural masses of circular and isotenoid toroids have been calculated in order to demonstrate the preferable performance and robustness of isotenoid toroids. It is concluded that the isotenoid toroid has significantly lower weight than the circular one at any equal volume. Therefore the structural performance of composite toroids can be remarkably improved using the isotenoid-based cross sections determined by the present method.

Since the method outlined here can only be considered as a simple approach of the toroids design based on the netting theory, an extended version has to be created, based on the continuum theory. This is part of current research.

References

1. Kim C U, Kang J H, Hong C S, Kim C G. "Optimal design of filament wound structures under internal pressure based on the semi-geodesic path algorithm". *Compos. Struct.*, 2005; 67(4):443-452.
2. Koussios S, Bergsma O K, Mitchell G. "Non-geodesic filament winding on generic shells of revolution". *Proc. IMechE Part L: J. Materials: Design and Applications*, 2005; 219(1):25-35.
3. Mahdi E, Sahari BB, Hamouda AMS, Khalid YA. "An experimental investigation into crushing behaviour of filament-wound laminated cone-cone intersection composite shell". *Compos. Struct.*, 2001; 51(3): 211-219.
4. Liang C, Chen H, Wang C. "Optimum design of dome contour for filament-wound composite pressure vessels based on a shape factor". *Compos. Struct.*, 2002; 58(4): 469-482.
5. Zu L, He Q X, Ni Q Q. "Pattern design for non-geodesic winding toroidal pressure vessels". *Proc. 16th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Jul. 2007, Kyoto, Japan.
6. Zu L. *Structural Design and Damage Identification of Filament-wound Toroidal Vessels*. Master Thesis. Xi'an University of Technology, China, 2007.
7. Li S G, Cook J. "An analysis of filament overwound toroidal pressure vessels and optimum design of such structures". *Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology*, 2002; 124(2): 215-222.
8. Jiang X Z, Fei C D, Ma G F. "Filament winding process of toroidal vessels". *Fiber composites*, 2005; 41(1): 41-43.
9. Koussios S. *Filament Winding: A Unified Approach*. PhD Thesis report, Design and Production of Composite Structures Group, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology, Delft, 2004.
10. Koussios S, Beukers A. "Composing composites: a paradigm of reversed design". *J. Design Research*, 2007; 5(3): 302-316.
11. Park J S, Hong C S, Kim C G, Kim C U. "Analysis of filament wound structures considering the change of winding angles through the thickness direction". *Compos. Struct.*, 2002; 55(1): 63-71.
12. Zu L, Koussios S, Beukers A. "Pattern design and optimization for filament wound toroidal pressure vessels". *Proc. 23rd Annual Conference of the American Society for Composites*, Memphis, TN, September 2008.